

Message from the WHPC@SC23 Workshop Chairs

November 3, 2023

The WHPC workshop aims to raise awareness and address issues around diversity and inclusion within the HPC community and workforce. Traditionally, our workshop series has focused on gender diversity and issues primarily facing women. New this year, we are putting an increased emphasis on diversity and inclusion of both women and men from underrepresented groups. By explicitly broadening our scope, we are increasing participation from other minority groups and particularly those individuals who feel marginalized across multiple dimensions.

One of the critical contributions of this workshop series to SC, and the wider community, is providing the workshop's early career presenters with their first justifiable reason for attending not just the WHPC workshop, but the broader SC conference. We elevate the profile of these early career researchers through peer-reviewed abstract submissions for lightning talks. Each selected speaker is matched with an experienced mentor from the SC community for formal mentoring, leading up to the SC workshop.

As part of our commitment to the success of our early career speakers, WHPC is able to provide a travel grant for two individuals. Relaunched in 2023, these travel grants were created by the WHPC Championship Program to fund women and men from underrepresented groups to attend high-profile HPC conferences. We are proud to highlight this year's awardees Leslie Cook (Midwestern State University) and Babar Khan (Technical University Darmstadt).

For the first time in 2023, we are compiling a subset of lightning talk abstracts to publish in a formal archive. We hope that this archive will highlight the research contributions and efforts of our early career and underrepresented speakers and bring them to the attention of the broader HPC community.

Submission Review Committee

- Anjus George, Oak Ridge National Laboratory
- Anna Weatherburn, Durham University, England
- Ben Durham, University of York, England
- Connor Aird, University College London
- James Perry, EPCC, University of Edinburgh
- Jean Luca Bez, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
- Jean M. Sexton, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
- Jose Manuel Monsalve Diaz, Argonne National Laboratory
- Joy Kitson, University of Maryland
- Krista Coleman, Harvard University
- Laura Moran, EPCC, University of Edinburgh
- Maria Camila Roa Carvajal, University of Tennessee Knoxville
- Marion Weinzerl, University of Cambridge
- Phuong Nguyen, University of Tennessee, Knoxville
- Tobias Weinzierl, Durham University

Travel Grant Review Committee

- Shubhi Taneja, Worcester Polytechnic Institute
- Rasha Atwi, Stony Brook University
- Jie Ren, College of William and Mary
- Cristin Merritt, Alces Flight Ltd

WHPC@SC23 Organizing Committee

Workshop Co-chairs

Elsa Gonsiorowski, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory
Mozhgan K. Chimeh, NVIDIA

Communication Chair

Cristin Merritt, Alces Flight Ltd

Invited Talks Co-chairs

Marium Umar, Intel
Anjus George, Oak Ridge National Laboratory

Submission Co-chairs

Eleanor Broadway, EPCC, University of Edinburgh
Jessica Dagostini, University of California Santa Cruz

Mentoring Co-chairs

Caitlin Ross, Kitware, Inc
Ayesha Afzal, Erlangen National High Performance Computing Center